

INNOVATIVE METHODS IN TEACHING ENGLISH

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INTRODUCTION.

Modern methodology is rich in teaching methods and principles. Each of them has its own advantages and disadvantages, merits and defects, but none is perfect. So, it is very important to find out the exact method of teaching in a particular case. We share the view of Chen Jiamy, who considers that the best method is one where a specific effect is obtained in a specific context. Choices of methods, then, should vary with different purposes, ages groups, and stages of mental development, etc (Chen Jiamu, 1997). Today the transformations, which are actively occurring in our country, have lead to people's demand for learning foreign languages. Most of them are looking forward to acquiring such a level in knowing language when he / she has certain basic skills of a foreign language and will possess all the qualities necessary for self-perfection of knowledge in it. Some of them need foreign languages to be able to communicate in everyday life, the other – to be effective in profession and adjoining spheres of activities [1. P. 53].

So, the results of their learning a foreign language are to be factually learned knowledge and competencies, personal development, self-dependence and creative search, an ability to continue learning the language on a higher level. To realize this task it is necessary to organize educational process in such a way so that it assists in effective realization of people's aims in learning foreign languages.

Skills

The skills are suggested to develop person's readiness to perform fluent communication in English and creative acts while solving different tasks: – on the level of reading, writing, listening, speaking; – on the level of confident use of the received knowledge in practical activity or work. The formation of knowledge, abilities and skills of students in learning foreign languages are to be considered the main indicator of competencies development (general and specific ones). Speaking about teaching adults we must say that it can be a very rewarding and enriching experience.

In terms of the teaching of English to adults, the right methods to adopt should be multipurposeoriented, mainly concerned with the characteristics of adults. In others words, with a fully developed mental power, the adults own modes of thinking, memory capacity, imitation ability, strengths and weaknesses, etc., and above all, how to make the best of them are the starting points for decisions about teaching methodology. Today we consider it necessary to use innovative methods and technologies in teaching English to adults.

Innovative methods and technologies represent an innovative trend in education, based on domestic and global trends, best practices and traditions [2. P. 75]. In accordance with the definitions of most dictionaries «innovation» is an introduced innovation, providing qualitative growth of processes or products' efficiency required by the market. Innovation is the final result of human intellectual activity, his imagination, creative processes, discoveries, inventions and rationalization.

Today, the concept of «innovation» is interpreted broadly. In the world economic literature repeatedly emphasizes the connection between the ideas of potential scientific and technological advances and their reality in new products and technologies. Innovation is defined as the process in which an invention or idea acquires the economic content. Joseph Schumpeter treats innovation as a new scientific and organized by a combination of production factors, motivated entrepreneurial spirit.

With regard to education innovation is considered to be the result of introduced innovation, which is revealed in the form of new content, methods, forms of organization of educational process or advanced technical training tools used in practice, or a new approach to social services in the field of education. Innovative methods and technologies of teaching today are gaining increasing recognition and new opportunities associated with the establishment of interpersonal interaction through external dialogue in the process of assimilation of educational material, as well as contribute to the implementation of the principle of continuity of knowledge transfer, formation of competencies, personal qualities and meta-professional ones [3. P. 89]. As for teaching adults it should be effective first of all. Part of being a successful adult educator involves understanding how adults learn best. Adults have special needs and requirements as learners. That's why the methodologists point out some of the common learning characteristics of adult language and literacy learners :

- 1) learners are goal-driven.
- 2) Language and literacy are social processes that involve interaction with others.
- 3) Language and literacy development require risk taking.
- 4) Language and literacy develop when the target language is slightly above the current level of proficiency of the user.
- 5) Language and literacy development require focus, engagement and practice.
- 6) Language and literacy are multi-dimensional and require different kinds of interactions with different kinds of genres.
- 7) Language and literacy develop through interactions with tasks that require cognitive involvement.
- 8) Language and literacy develop more deeply if skills are connected to an overall topic, theme or context.

So, there are so many different innovative methods of teaching adults which together with the traditional ones help us to instruct adults while learning foreign languages and organize the work in class. To conclude, the major concern is aiming at how to achieve the best result or a relatively better one in a given context. Adoptions of teaching methods involve such factors as purposes, age groups and stages of mental development. In our opinion the method of direct instruction and the method of electronic self-directed education are comparatively found suitable for adult beginners while method of pedagogic studio work and the method of interdisciplinary projecting are advisable suggest for those at intermediate and advanced level. Guided composition should be practised, combining two or three, even four skills together.

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